

IMPROVEMENT OF THE REGULATION OF TOURISM ACTIVITIES IN MODERN CONDITIONS

Elena Potekhina*, Yuriy Putrik**, Sergey Barsukov***, Anastasiya Smirnova****, Elena Tretyak*****

Abstract

The aim of the study lies in improving approaches to the regulation of tourism activities in modern conditions. We consider that the orientations of the regulation of the development of tourism activities are represented by the normative and legal, economic, social and information spheres. The study analyzes and identifies the favorable conditions for each sphere, evidencing that: (a) in the normative and legal spheres, conditions should be created for the development of public-private partnerships through the design of strategies for the development of tourism clusters and the use of the instruments of tax investment loans for tourism enterprises; (b) in the economic sphere it is necessary to develop effective organizational and economic support measures for the promotion of the brand of the Russian Federation on international markets for tourism services; c) in the social sphere it is necessary to develop social tourism, in particular, family, children, business and green tourism, moreover, it is noted, d) in the information sphere, the desirability of developing cooperation with institutions of higher education and support and public recognition of the status of the subjects of tourism activity.

Keywords: Cluster; Public policy; Budget; Capital; State; Tourism.

MELHORIA DA REGULAMENTAÇÃO DAS ATIVIDADES TURÍSTICAS EM CONDIÇÕES MODERNAS**Resumo**

O objetivo do estudo reside na melhoria das abordagens à regulamentação das atividades turísticas em condições modernas. Consideramos que as orientações da regulamentação do desenvolvimento das atividades turísticas são representadas pelas esferas normativa e jurídica, econômica, social e de informação. O estudo analisa e identifica as condições favoráveis para cada esfera, evidenciando que: a) nas esferas normativa e jurídica, devem ser criadas condições para o desenvolvimento de parcerias público-privadas através da concepção de estratégias para o desenvolvimento de clusters turísticos e a utilização dos instrumentos de empréstimo de investimento fiscal para empresas turísticas; b) na esfera econômica é necessário desenvolver medidas eficazes de apoio organizacional e econômico para a promoção da marca da Federação Russa nos mercados internacionais de serviços turísticos; c) na esfera social, é necessário desenvolver o turismo social, em particular, o turismo familiar, infantil, empresarial e verde, além disso, nota-se, d) na esfera de informação, a conveniência de desenvolver a cooperação com instituições de ensino superior e o apoio e reconhecimento público do estatuto dos sujeitos da atividade turística.

Palavras-chave: Aglomerado; Políticas públicas; Orçamento; Capital; Estado; Turismo.

MEJORA DE LA REGULACIÓN DE LAS ACTIVIDADES TURÍSTICAS EN CONDICIONES MODERNAS**Resumen**

El propósito del estudio radica en la mejora de los enfoques de la regulación de las actividades turísticas en las condiciones modernas. Consideramos que las orientaciones de la regulación del desarrollo de las actividades turísticas están representadas por las esferas normativa y jurídica, económica, social y de información. El estudio analiza e identifica las condiciones favorables para cada ámbito, evidenciando que: (a) en el ámbito normativo y legal, se deben crear las condiciones para el desarrollo de asociaciones público-privadas mediante el diseño de estrategias para el desarrollo de clusters turísticos y el uso de los instrumentos de préstamos de inversión fiscal para las empresas turísticas; (b) en el ámbito económico es necesario desarrollar medidas eficaces de apoyo organizativo y económico para la promoción de la marca de la Federación Rusa en los mercados internacionales de servicios turísticos; c) en el ámbito social es necesario desarrollar el turismo social, en particular, la familia, los niños, los negocios y el turismo verde, además, se señala, d) en el ámbito de la información, la conveniencia de desarrollar la cooperación con las instituciones de educación superior y el apoyo y el reconocimiento público de la condición de los sujetos de la actividad turística.

Palabras clave: Grupo; Políticas públicas; Presupuesto; Capital; Estado; Turismo.

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* Doctor of Economic Sciences, Russian State Social University, Moscow, Russian Federation. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7995-7424> [elengapotechina@mail.ru]

** Doctor of Historic Sciences, Likhachev Russian Research Institute for Cultural and Natural Heritage, Moscow, Russian Federation. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1053-8595> [putrik@iist.ru]

*** PhD Candidate of Historic Sciences, Shakhly Automobile and Road Construction Institute (branch) of South Russian State Polytechnic University (NPI) named after M.I. Platov, Shakhly, Rostov region, Russian Federation. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9188-4777> [sergei-mb@mail.ru]

**** PhD Candidate of Historic Sciences, Vyatka State University, Kirov, Russian Federation. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0202-3807> [asyanastya29@gmail.com]

***** Senior Lecturer, Associate professor, Moscow Polytechnic University, Moscow, Russian Federation. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4383-4630> [tretyak.le@yandex.ru]

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the most promising sectors of the world economy that has a considerable impact on the development of the state is the tourism industry (Ulema et al., 2021). Even during the crisis, the importance of the industry is constantly growing, because tourism contributes to an increase in jobs and an inflow of foreign exchange earnings into the country, replenishes the budgets at various levels, as well as attracts entrepreneurs with small start-up capitals and quick payback periods (Gao et al., 2022).

The geographical location of the Russian Federation, its natural resources, climate, and historical, cultural, and recreational potential are the main prerequisites for the development of tourism (Abbas et al., 2021). However, the development of the tourism industry in Russia is chaotic, there is no purposeful state policy on tourism, which leads to an outflow of funds abroad due to the significant share of outbound tourism (Vorobey, 2021).

In addition, the development of the Russian tourism industry relates to the European model of state regulation, which is based on the proclamation of tourism as one of the priorities of development at the state level, where the issue of tourism development is addressed at a high state level by the Federal Agency for Tourism, which focuses on addressing common issues of effective public policy to create a positive tourist image and promote the country brand.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

The problems of the development of the tourism industry have been reflected in the works of various scholars. In particular, Burykina (2021) notes that the rational regulation of tourism activities should contribute to the creation of a competitive national tourism product that can satisfy tourism needs to the maximum and ensure, on this basis, the integrated development of the regions in the Russian Federation while maintaining ecological balance and cultural heritage.

Vidischeva (2021) emphasizes that the development of tourism activities is ensured by creating tourism infrastructure and conditions for increasing the attractiveness of regions for foreign and domestic tourists, as well as improving the quality of tourism services.

In this case, according to Kulakova (2019), tourism is subject to state regulation, and, therefore, the state forms a tourism policy. In the scholar's opinion, the tourism policy of the state is an activity to develop the tourism industry and the subjects of the tourism market, improve the forms of tourist services for citizens, and strengthen their political and economic potential.

The tourism policy of the state is a set of forms, methods, and directions of state influence on the functioning of the tourism sector to achieve specific goals in preserving and developing the national economic complex. The mechanism for implementing the state's tourism policy covers the development of concepts for the development of tourism, as well as the preparation of targeted programs for the development of tourism both at the level of the state as a whole and at the level of individual regional markets (Nikitashina, Urmatskikh, 2021).

One cannot but agree with Sachenok (2021) that the main areas of regulation of tourism activities are the protection of the rights of travelers, the interests of producers of the tourism product, and the support of domestic and inbound tourism. In the scholar's opinion, the forms of such support range from direct investment in the formation of tourism infrastructure to tax and customs benefits that stimulate investment.

Iudina (2019) rightly writes that there are several components of policy that in one way or another affect tourism. These are economic policy, passenger transportation policy, social policy, territorial policy, cultural policy, and leisure policy.

However, despite the significant number of scientific works and developments devoted to the development of tourism, many issues remain unresolved. Insufficient attention is paid to the directions of improving state regulation of tourist activity in the Russian Federation, especially in the spheres of information and marketing.

3 METHODS

The study was carried out based on Russian State Social University, Likhachev Russian Research Institute for Cultural and Natural Heritage, Shakhty Automobile and Road Construction Institute (branch) of South Russian state Polytechnic University (NPI) named after M.I. Platov, Vyatka State University and Moscow Polytechnic University in 2021-2022.

The methodological basis of the study consists in the integrated use of a set of general and specialized scientific research methods. In determining the study methodology, we proceed from the complexity and interdisciplinarity of the subject of research. Therefore, at the basis of the study methodology lies a systematic approach, which is necessitated by the complex nature of the study and through which we consider the research problem to be the analysis of an integral system and its constituent elements.

The study of the problem of state regulation of tourist activity is made possible through the use of a number of other scientific methods, in particular, the specific and exploratory, historical and discrete, logical

(comparative), economic and statistical analysis, synthesis, sociological research, structural and functional, and comparative methods. In this study, we make an attempt to integrate the scientific-theoretical and empirical levels of knowledge.

The selection of sources was carried out considering the coverage of state regulation of tourism activities. We used legislative and regulatory acts, materials of state and local authorities, and scientific publications of Russian and foreign researchers on the regulation of tourism activities (Lukiyanchuk, et al., 2020; Malyugina, et al., 2020; Ogloblina, et al., 2020). We paid special attention to scientific articles related to state regulation of tourism.

Structurally, the study involved a consistent analysis of the regulation of tourism activities in the Russian Federation, as well as identifying the components of its improvement. At the first stage, based on the analysis and generalization of scientific concepts and points of view, we systematized the substantiation of the category of state tourism policy and determined the role of state regulation in general and in the tourism sector in particular.

At the second stage, based on the studies of the features of state regulation in the tourism sector, we substantiated the goals of state regulation in tourism activities in the Russian Federation and showed the features of its tourism brand.

At the third stage, we determined the directions of state regulation of the development of tourism activities in the Russian Federation, which are represented by the legal, economic, social, and information spheres.

In the course of the study, it is planned to develop approaches to the analysis of the problems of regulating tourism activities and provide substantiation for the behavior strategies of participants in the tourism market under modern conditions. Furthermore, an objective is set to provide substantiation for approaches to the assessment of the quality of tourism activities and to define and formulate the main directions for the development of tourism.

4 RESULTS

Recently, the Government of the Russian Federation has prepared a large package of measures to reform the system of financial guarantees for tour operators. This is due to the fact that the current system of financial guarantees, which provides for deductions to the reserve and personal liability of the tour operator, is not fair. It does not allow the tourist to receive any compensation or a significant part of the paid tour in the event of the bankruptcy of the tour operator.

In addition, it is planned to create a collective responsibility fund for tour operators. Corresponding

payments to it by market participants will not lead to any significant increase in the cost of tours and will not become an excessive or additional burden on the business that currently operates in the legal field.

Also, President of the Russian Federation Vladimir Putin signed Law No. 48-FZ "On Amendments to the Federal Law 'On the Basics of Tourism in the Russian Federation'". According to the adopted law, the register of travel agents is a federal information resource that will contain information about travel agents and subagents. It will be maintained by the authorized federal body electronically on its website in cooperation with other federal systems, as well as with systems of tour operators and travel agents.

The law prescribes the information that is to be included in the register of travel agents, including what will be automatically generated in the register. Tour operators will also have to independently, no later than three working days from the date of concluding an agreement with a travel agent for the promotion and sale of a tourism product (as well as indicating the possibility or impossibility of a subagency), form data on such an agreement in the register of travel agents.

Entering information by the tour operator will be carried out using a personal account on the official website of the authorized federal body. The grounds for refusing to enter information into the unified register of travel agents include the absence of such information, its inconsistency, or the presence in these registers of an entry on the termination of the activity of a travel agent.

At the same time, the exclusion of information about the travel agent, subagent from the unified register of travel agents, or the termination of their activities does not relieve the tour operator from the obligation to ensure the provision of services purchased by the tourist.

Under these conditions, negative trends are the main reason behind the low tourist attractiveness of the Russian Federation compared to competitors' resorts is the obsolescence of the material and technical base and infrastructure.

Based on foreign experience, it can be argued that the main objectives of state regulation of tourist activity are to ensure the rights of citizens to rest, freedom of movement, and other rights when traveling, to ensure the development of the tourism industry for it to meet the needs of citizens when traveling, and to create the necessary conditions for activities aimed at improving the health of tourists (see Figure 1).

In this regard, the main directions of an efficient state tourism policy need to cover the legal, economic, social, and information spheres. In the meantime, the normative and legal sphere provides for the development of appropriate legislative acts and amendments to the existing laws.

Figure 1. The objectives of public administration of tourism activities in the Russian Federation

Source: own elaboration.

It is also necessary to take into consideration the procedures of licensing, certification, and standardization in the provision of services and the assessment of the level of tourist safety during the tour, since it is in human nature to act differently in unfamiliar situations and unusual circumstances.

Therefore, in order to promote the development of tourism activities in the Russian Federation, it is advisable to use one of the forms of public-private partnership – concession, which presents a promising tool for attracting investment in the public sector over the long term. In accordance with Russian law, a concession agreement combines certain elements of renting, leasing, and other transactions, which allow accounting for the interests of both parties involved, distributing the potential risks between them.

At the basis of this form of public-private partnership lies the establishment of optimal conditions for stable and mutually beneficial relations between the state and the private sector, which acts as an investor (Wani et al., 2022). Thus, the private party of a concession contract gains access to profitable projects in the sphere of tourism and recreation and is offered tax relief by the partner, being attracted by the support of the state as a guarantor of credit.

Furthermore, the introduction of a partnership between the private and public sectors in tourism contributes to the development of infrastructure, the renewal of the material and technical base of accommodation facilities, and the provision of competitive tourist services, thus forming a positive image and promoting the brand of the Russian Federation as an attractive country in the international market of tourist services.

The above-mentioned stimulates the development of innovative structures in the sphere of tourism – tourism clusters, special economic zones that

contribute to the harmonious integrated development of all sectors of the economy related to tourism, forming a closed production cycle, enable the provision and production of tourism products and services competitive at the national and international levels, provide selective support for tourism activities in regions with a high level of tourist attraction, and increase the investment attractiveness of regions.

Additionally, the obsolescence of the material and technical base of healthcare institutions does not allow for high income, which, in turn, leads to the lack of renewal of the existing sanatorium-resort and tourist services. There is a need for additional sources of investment for the development of the tourism sphere.

The rather high entrepreneurial risk of investment in the Russian Federation results in low rates of foreign investment and actualized the value of financing of the sanatorium-resort sphere by the state, which utilizes the instruments of investment tax crediting as the basis of the regional investment policy.

In this case, investment tax credit presents the deferral of profit tax payment granted to the subject of entrepreneurial activity for a certain period in order to improve its financial resources for the implementation of innovative programs with subsequent compensation of the deferred amounts in the form of additional tax revenues from the overall growth of profit, which will be obtained in accordance with the current legislation by means of the implementation of innovative programs.

The investment tax credit is typically granted in accordance with the fundamental principles, namely: repayment, maturity, remuneration, and purposeful use (i.e. it is appropriate to provide it for innovative programs and projects that go in line with the scientific and technological priorities).

The specific features of obtaining investment tax credit are that the credit is returned in the form of

increased tax payments due to the overall growth of profits obtained as a result of the implementation of an innovative project – the creation of a tourism cluster.

In contrast to regular bank credits, the investment tax credit for tourism enterprises does not require additional credit resources and payment of interest on certain conditions, which makes investments onerous, is provided for a specific innovative project, and is systemic in nature.

The advantages of granting investment tax credits on the part of the state are that it promotes the development of innovation and investment in the tourism sphere, increases the tax base and revenues to the state budget, promotes employment, and stimulates enterprises to abandon shadow economy since it implies increased attention from the tax authorities. As for the private sector, the investment tax credit makes it possible to replenish investment resources by implementing promising innovation and investment projects.

The conditions for granting investment tax credit include a stable financial condition of the borrower, the focus on investment in the investor's use of their own financial resources, a sound business plan that once put to practice, will ensure higher efficiency of service activities, and the growth of total revenue and profit tax amount as a source of compensation for the investment tax credit.

Tax investment credit is provided for the period of implementation of a project or program, but for no more than three years, by deferring tax liabilities accrued from the profits of the business entity as part of implementing an innovation and investment project. Interest for the use of such credit shall be accrued on the amount of deferred tax liability on this tax at the rate of 50% of the discount rate of the Central Bank of the Russian Federation calculated for each day of credit use and paid monthly.

The aforementioned is of relevance for the creation of tourism clusters in regions with a high level of tourist attractiveness as an innovative form of development of the tourism industry. As a result of introducing such a formation, the socio-economic

condition of the regions and the country as a whole can improve, providing competitive tourist services on the national and international markets and ensuring a closed cycle of production.

The suggested crediting for tourist enterprises will stimulate the development of innovative services, in particular: SPA-services, cosmetology services, aesthetic dentistry; aroma-, speleo- (treatment by the atmosphere of salt mines), phyto- and bioresonance therapy.

5 DISCUSSION

Our conclusions differ from those of Arbulú et al. (2017), Pfueller et al. (2011), Luo et al. (2022), who note that the basis of public-private partnership is the establishment of optimal conditions for stable and mutually beneficial relations between the state and the private sector, which acts as an investor. Thus, the private party to the concession agreement has access to profitable projects in the tourism and recreational sectors, reducing tax pressure from the partner and being attracted by the support of the state as a guarantor of lending.

Furthermore, considerable attention needs to be paid to the development of effective measures to support the promotion of the tourism brand of the Russian Federation in international markets, especially at present, when tourism is going through difficult times. After all, the brand is a vital element for the development of a tourist destination (Kang et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2022).

The development and further positioning of the Russian Federation with the new tourism brand will serve as an impetus for the development of tourism in the country and presents a key step towards the strategy of tourism development in the state. Studies show that the tourism brand is part of a systemic program for the promotion of the country in the world and improving the tourism sphere within the country. Its widespread use will support the tourist flow (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Elements of the tourism brand of the Russian Federation.

Source: own elaboration.

Furthermore, it is advisable to create a separate body tasked with marketing activities, specifically: the promotion of the national tourist product at different levels by means of creating tourist websites on the Internet; forming the positive tourism image and brand of the country using slogans as a tool of marketing policy and working on the principle of “not a day without tourism news”; introducing regional programs for the development of the tourism sector.

Since one of the main characteristics that distinguish the Russian Federation from other world countries is hospitality, the slogan to be used for the country can be “Hospitality in a Russian way”. In a survey on the factors that encourage to visit the Russian Federation, foreigners name: picturesque nature (30%); architecture and cultural and historical sites (30%); hospitality and sincerity of the local population (10%); national cuisine (7%); the beauty of Russian women (6%).

It is also advisable to hold “Russian Federation Week” seminars, forums, and conferences abroad. Such events will help to attract investment, improve tourist attractiveness, creating a positive image of the country, as noted in international agreements on cooperation, simplification of customs and visa procedures, the development of group travel, and the growth of inbound tourism (Streimikiene et al., 2021).

A fundamental aspect of promoting a tourism brand is creating a positive tourist image, which should involve a stimulus to visit the most attractive tourist sites and the familiarization of tourists with the history of the country. The methods advisable for the promotion of the tourism brand of the Russian Federation include: posting information on portals in at least 5 languages; conducting marketing research for the formation of customer loyalty; Internet fairs; blogging; information tours for bloggers (Bassols-Gardella, Coromina, 2022).

The reliability of the presented approaches is supported by the fact that the majority of foreign tourists wishing to visit the Russian Federation do not have access to information, which is why it is currently a relevant task to borrow the experience of the educational sphere and create a webometric rating of tour operators that would analyze the degree of representation of tourism activities on the Internet (Agamirova, Agamirova, Lebedeva, Lebedev, & Ilkevich, 2017; Markova, Listopad, Shelygov, Fedorov, & Kiselevich, 2021; Zavalko, Kozhina, Zhakevich, Matyunina, & Lebedeva, 2017).

The motive behind the creation of a webometric rating of tour operators is increasing demand for tourist travel around the world, reinforcing people’s secondary needs. The methodology for creating a webometric rating should include a certain number of web pages

provided by search engines and a certain number of unique external links to websites (Lin, Huang, 2006).

Attention should be paid to the web page of the Federal Agency for Tourism of the Russian Federation, which needs to be supplemented. In particular, it is advisable to post information on the rates of visits to Russia country by foreign tourists and a detailed presentation of developed attractive routes indicating their cost of services, the duration of stay of tourists at each point of the route, the number of tourists in the group, the type and number of vehicles involved in servicing tourists.

Moreover, one of the directions of state support for tourism is the social sphere that implies the creation of the necessary conditions for rehabilitation and rest for all segments of the population, with special attention being paid to children’s, family, and green tourism. In this case, the development of family and children’s tourism is one of the sustainable segments of the tourism industry development.

At the same time, the health of young people tends to deteriorate, which is explained by the negative socio-economic, environmental, and psycho-emotional factors. Thus, the goals of the active development of children’s tourism include healthcare and increasing the general educational level of a child’s development as a person, for example, by creating children’s camps with an in-depth study of foreign languages and entertainment, educational, amateur, and animation programs.

6 CONCLUSION

To draw a summary, it can be stated that the directions of state regulation of the development of tourist activities are represented by four spheres: the normative and legal, the economic, the social, and the information sphere. It is established that conditions for the development of public-private partnerships should be created in the normative and legal sphere by means of designing strategies for the development of tourism clusters and the use of the tools of tax investment lending for tourism enterprises.

In the economic sphere, effective measures of organizational and economic support need to be developed to promote the brand of the Russian Federation in the international tourism market. In the social sphere, there is a need for the development of social tourism, particularly family, children’s, business, and green tourism.

In addition, the development of cooperation with higher educational institutions and support and public recognition of the status of the subjects of tourist activity is noted to be expedient. For this reason, special attention has to be paid to the information sphere and

proposals on the creation of a webometric rating of tour operators, which should be entrusted to the central body of state regulation of the tourism sector.

At the same time, the effective development of tourism activities requires an optimal management system. Therefore, what is to be considered as the most perfected form of territorial organization of the tourism sphere at the regional level are recreational centers, which should take the form of separate settlements with a set of recreational institutions or individual facilities acting as central points for the formation of tourist complexes.

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Table 1. CRediT author statement

Term	Definition	Author 1	A.2	A.3	A.4	A.5
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	+	+	+	+	+
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	+	+	+	+	+
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components	+	+	+	+	+
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	+	+	+	+	+
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data	+	+	+	+	+
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	+	+	+	+	+
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	+	+	+	+	+
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	+	+	+	+	+
Writing – Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	+	+	+	+	+
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or post-publication stages	+	+	+	+	+
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/data presentation	+	+	+	+	+
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team	+	+	+	+	+
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	+	+	+	+	+
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication	+	+	+	+	+

Source: adapted from Elsevier (2022, s/p), based upon Brand et al. (2015).

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